

ADAPT Open Science Policy

Overview

Aligning Discoveries Across Psychedelic Therapies (ADAPT) brings together a consortium of researchers to create a robust, transparent, and collaborative psychedelic research ecosystem that advances discovery and therapeutic potential. Open science practices are foundational to this mission: they accelerate discovery, increase reproducibility, and ensure that findings in this nascent field are broadly accessible and verifiable.

The ADAPT Open Science Policy aims to maximize the impact and reusability of research outputs. If jurisdictional requirements conflict with any part of this policy, please consult ADAPT staff. We will work with you to navigate these obligations while upholding our open science standards. The Policy will be operationalized into a Handbook, which will be linked to from adaptrroadmap.org, and used to support and monitor compliance.

Policy Requirements

1. Anticipate Data, Code, and Protocol Sharing

Requirement: Research ethics applications and informed consent forms must be constructed to allow for broad sharing of de-identified individual-level human participant data. Data, code, and protocols, should be centrally captured with robust management plans that ensure their integrity, and should be made available to members of your ADAPT-funded project as soon as possible.

2. Register ADAPT-Funded Studies

Requirement: ADAPT-funded studies must be registered to osf.io/registries. Registrations for exploratory studies should focus on the intent of the study and the methods. Registrations for confirmatory studies must also include itemized hypotheses, statistical plans to test the hypotheses, and well-defined outcome measures. For more information on what to register for an ADAPT-funded study, see the [ADAPT Study Registration Policy](#).

3. Deposit Research Outputs

Requirement: De-identified individual-level human participant data must be deposited to an ADAPT-designated Analytics Platform and Long-Term Data Repository – Bridge Analytics. All other research outputs generated as part of an ADAPT-funded study must be deposited to a community-recognized repository.

Research Outputs to deposit include:

- Biosamples and/or lab materials (e.g., cell lines, organisms, reagents) – if generated
- Experimental protocols, methods, and procedures
- De-identified data in as raw a form as is practical

- Code and scripts used to preprocess and clean data
- Cleaned data (processed, quality-controlled data)
- Code and scripts used to analyze and visualize data
- Algorithms, AI models, and other tools
- Preprints, posted no later than the time of submission to a journal
- **Null and negative results:** ADAPT strongly encourages the reporting of null and negative results. As psychedelic research ramps up, these findings are particularly valuable to the field and should not be withheld.

4. Ensure Access

Requirement: All research outputs generated as part of an ADAPT-funded study must be licensed to allow for unrestricted reuse (other than individual-level human participant data), be accompanied with sufficient metadata to allow re-analysis by third parties, and be made broadly available in a timely manner (no later than the time of posting a preprint, or within 12 months of completing data collection, whichever comes first). Individual-level human participant data must allow for controlled-access rights to bona fide researchers in perpetuity.

Implementation:

- Access may be restricted and/or delayed to the extent required to comply with ethical guidelines, privacy requirements, and Institutional Review Board approval, and to safeguard study integrity (e.g., prevent breaking a blind)
- Recommended reuse terms for research outputs include **CCo** (non-sensitive data), **CC BY** (text-based documents), **MIT** (code), and **OpenMTA** (biological materials)

5. Identify Research Resources

Requirement: All research resources used and generated in a study must be identified in relevant documents (e.g., in preprints, study protocols).

Implementation:

- Use Availability Statements to identify where research resources used and generated in the study can be accessed (see Policy Requirement 3 for a list of research outputs)
- Use persistent identifiers when citing research resources (e.g., DOIs, RRIIDs, accession numbers) and when identifying research contributors (ORCIDiDs)
- In all research outputs, acknowledge ADAPT funding

Compliance

Compliance with the ADAPT Open Science Policy is a condition of ADAPT funding. ADAPT staff will work collaboratively with grantees to support compliance and address challenges. If barriers to compliance arise, grantees should contact ADAPT staff as early as possible to discuss solutions.